

Adjustment Across Different Life Stages: Study of Psychology Challenges and Counselling Approach

Bravishi Slag¹ & Noopur Jaswal²

1. Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Quantum University, Roorkee (Haridwar) UK

2. Associate Professor, Department of Humanities and Social Sciences,
Quantum University, Roorkee (Haridwar) UK Email: sonapanwar007@gmail.com

Received : 19/02/2026

1st BPR : 27/02/2026

2nd BPR : 07/03/2026

Accepted : 15/03/2026

Abstract

Adjustment is a necessary process that every individual requires in their life. It helps them to settle down in any situation, in any condition of their life. Working like an equilibrium, it balances out a person's life, helping them in their growth throughout their life as they become more adaptable and learn to adjust in their life. Every individual goes through these few stages in their life with no exceptions i.e., childhood, adolescence, adulthood, old age. They experience different types of challenges in each of the life stages. With the time, they complete their stages going through several transitions developing skills like dealing with peer pressure or family pressure, starting a career, retirement etc. It differs from person to person's life that how their transitions occur, they may go smoothly or rough with lots of ups and downs, facing different issues (i.e., psychological challenges and others), struggling, seeking help or guidance yet only few of them gets it, others feel stuck. Here counsellor play a pivotal in that person's life. A counsellor helps an individual in figuring out their issue, getting a better understanding of the problem by counselling them, improving their problem-solving skills as well as logical reasoning that also contributes in overcoming their struggles helping them in their adjustment process.

Keywords: Adjustment, Life Stages, Psychology Challenges, Counselling Approach.

Introduction

Any human-being living in this world is affected by several factors. It can be physical, social, emotional or cognitive. It's a human tendency to wish, to want or shift things as they like but reality is different. Not everything goes by our will or in a manner like how we want. A person's mind goes through several different thoughts and cognitive processes, they may be practical or imaginary. And in most of the cases either they want that thing to come true or it has already happened in the past, only a number of people think about their present on the daily basis and this is also the reason that why they remain stuck in their life. Because they mostly remain drown in the thoughts of past or in worry for the future, they generally forget about the present. The process of adjustment is required in every individual's life, this fact cannot be ignored. In each stage of the life, it is needed and required for the ideal growth and development of an individual. No matter what status, time, situation it is, a person has to be adaptable and learn how to adjust in any condition of their life. Many times, people struggle, facing multiple issues at the same time creating a feeling of frustration and pressure or they simply don't find a way out of their problem, feeling stuck. They might also not open up to anyone which can create a barrier between them and other people. This is similar to the generational gap. People born and living in previous generations did not focus on these issues that much but in this upcoming era, or we can say since the starting of gen-z generation, it has become a highlighted topic. Nowadays people focus and understand things more deeply than before. An individual's overall well-being (including psychologically) is necessary in their life for themselves and their surroundings as well because directly

or indirectly it affects the people around them e.g., family, friends, spouse, colleagues or anyone else present in their personal or professional life. In this, counsellor provides a supportive environment by helping those who seek help or need guidance, in developing coping strategies, setting realistic goals, making them aware about self-exploration, creating a safe space for them to open up, facilitating self-knowledge and growth etc. With proper guidance and counselling, a person facing psychological challenges can overcome from his/her issues. This can help them to find a way out and learn to adjust in their life.

Objectives

1. To study the role of adjustment in early childhood
2. To understand the overcoming struggles in adolescence
3. To understand the life transition in adulthood
4. To understand the adjustment process in old age

Review of Literature

Öngören, S. (2021) studied that counsellor play a significant role in children's adjustment to school i.e., academic, as well as emotional, social and behavioral areas throughout practicing different activities. Eslinger, Carolen (1992) researched that as many students nowadays face attention related issues, in this counselor can be a great help in resolving those issues. Kushendar, Kushendar & Mayra, Zara. (2021) found in their study that guidance and counseling in early childhood can help them to enhance their in-built qualities and foster themselves according to their own interests and talent. Safri, T., & Vajpeyi, L. (2016) found that parent-child relationship starting from the early childhood stage affects their adjustment process and their social life. Arum, Reny & Ignacio, Darwin. (2024) studied in their paper that adolescents could get benefitted from the peer counselling, helping in their self-adjustment. Sudiksha, Malik, P., Rawat, D., Aarti, & Simran. (2024) researched that the counselling, guidance can help students academically, emotionally, socially, psychologically as well as in career choices by providing them with the information. Chaudhary, A. K., & Shekhawat, B. R. (2024) have found that the developed and effective interventions can be implied as there's a good response of counseling on adolescence mental health. Vats, P. K., & Biswas, S. (2024) found in their study that the adjustment process is beneficial for adolescents as they become more resilient, self-aware, acquiring knowledge, emotionally intelligent helping them to also develop the coping strategies. Lane, J. (2014) found in their research that transformative counseling can be rewarding for emerging adults as it is a transition period for them and they experience instability in many situations in this period of opportunities. Richard A. Young, Sheila K. Marshall, Kristen Foulkes, Carla Haber, Celine S.M. Lee, Carey Penner, Hajara Rostram (2011) researched that the results can be satisfactory if counseling is introduced initially in their transition period to adulthood. Živčić-Bećirević, I., Smojver-Ažić, S., & Martinac Dorčić, T. (2020) found in their study that employed adults are at lower risk of psychological instability comparatively to unemployed men as they are not fully aware of an adult's role. Chaudhary, A. K., & Shekhawat, B. R. (2024) have studied that using different techniques and tools in counseling emotional instability can be balanced out, bringing stability in them. Hung, H. Y., Azman, A., & Jamir Singh, P. S. (2023) found in their research that psychological counseling can help in improving old people's behavioral functioning preserving their dignity for the betterment of their aging process. Owunebe, Anna. (2022) researched that in old people, anxiety and self-acceptance can be adjusted with the help of counseling. Fullen, M. C. (2016) found that counselors use various approaches to make a significant change for the later life of an individual, improving it. Leena, S. T., & Raju, S. (n.d.) researched that the mental health and the adjustment process of geriatric patients can be improved through psychological counseling.

These were the critical review of literature. We have taken the data from already published papers and articles. On the basis of the respective studies, these comments have been made. It was made sure that data is unbiased and kept out of unsurety of any results or comments.

Methodology

This paper titled "adjustment across different life stages: study of psychology challenges and counselling approach" is based on the secondary and qualitative data. We have studied different papers published and collected the data from various databases i.e., Google Scholar, Sage Journals, Research Gate, IJNRD and many different journals as well. It was made sure that the data remains unbiased and kept out from the unsured results.

Discussion

Early childhood is the first from the different stages of life. When an infant turns into a toddler, he/she learns many things and have to adjust with them for their growth and development. The child begins to do things on his own, making mistakes then trying to correct them. It's their tendency to explore new things as the world is new to them. In this, people around that child (i.e., guardians, teachers and counsellors) play a significant role. Kushendar, Kushendar & Mayra, Zara. (2021) found in their study that guidance and counseling in early childhood can help them to enhance their in-built qualities and foster themselves according to their own interests and talent. Safri, T., & Vajpeyi, L. (2016) found that parent-child relationship starting from the early childhood stage affects their adjustment process and their social life.

Adolescence is the period of puberty when a kid begins to develop mentally, physically, socially, their cognitive processes also become deeper, their thoughts become critical, making them ready for their next stage. As they experience hormonal changes and face transition for first time, then become really sensitive easily affected by things, irritable etc. This stage shapes an individual's personality that's why it's very important to focus on their adjustment process in this time period. Chaudhary, A. K., & Shekhawat, B. R. (2024) have found that the developed and effective interventions can be implied as there's a good response of counseling on adolescence mental health. Vats, P. K., & Biswas, S. (2024) found in their study that the adjustment process is beneficial for adolescents as they become more resilient, self-aware, acquiring knowledge, emotionally intelligent helping them to also develop the coping strategies.

As transition to the adulthood stage comes with lots of responsibilities, it's a must to focus on their process of adjustment. Initially, it begins with a mess if the individual is not ready enough. With the time and experience they become mature and learn to handle the situations. During this, they face instability various times. If a counselor enlightens them from the start of this particular stage, there are high chances of the low levels of struggle to be faced by them. Lane, J. (2014) found in their research that transformative counseling can be rewarding for emerging adults as it is a transition period for them and they experience instability in many situations in this period of opportunities. Carla Haber, Celine S.M. Lee, Carey Penner, Hajara Rostram (2011) researched that the results can be satisfactory if counseling is introduced initially in their transition period to adulthood.

Old age is the last stage of life. The individual becomes dependent on their family in this stage as they experience decline in their health and get ill easily. Their sensory organs may start to respond less as compare to when they were young. All these reasons can affect their mental health and thoughts. For this a counselor is highly recommended as they can help them with their adjustment process, improving their life in that stage as well. Many times, old people start to feel lonely thinking that no one understands them, here counselor can provide a supportive environment for them. Owunebe, Anna. (2022) researched that in old people, anxiety and self-acceptance can be adjusted with the help of counseling. Leena, S. T., & Raju, S. (n.d.) researched that the mental health and the adjustment process of geriatric patients can be improved through psychological counseling.

Conclusion

According this study it should be concluded that it does not matter which stage it is, an individual might require a counselor in any stage. This does not mean and they should go to the counselor in each stage of their life or in every little problem faced by them in adjustment the adjustment process. But when it is really needed as a counselor can help them to overcome from any psychological issue faced by them. This can provide them support with their problems in adjustment process.

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